

Asynchronous Communication Technologies and Implications on Classroom Management Skills and Teaching Approaches

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Abstract

Educators and researchers have been reviewing both positive and negative effects of Web 2.0. technologies on students' cognitive, affective and socio-interactive learning strategies. In that context, some educators have made research-informed decisions to implement interactive technologies (learning platforms, blogs, wikis, podcasts, content streaming providers and social networking sites) in order to cognitively engage their students and exploit the technologies' features to educational purposes. To that end, this research paper is a contribution in that regard as the paper reviews the most common Web 2.0. Technologies in the context of students and reports on the benefits of their features as well as their impacts on cognition, attitudes and motivation levels.

Introduction

One of the most challenging task for a human mind is to learn a foreign language. Ravichandran, Kretovic, Kirby, and Ghosh (2017) mention that some of the most difficult hurdles to overcome for students are writing and public speaking while learning a new language. The fear of making mistakes creates anxiety in students. It is highly related to the student's loss of self-esteem while learning a foreign language. However, the rapid growth of modern information technology in education, especially the Internet and language learning, is becoming increasingly broader and more profound.

Web 2.0 platforms have become a ubiquitous component of our daily lives (e.g., blogs, vlogs, video conferencing, wikis, social networking platforms). As Halili (2018) point out that millions of people today use Web 2.0 technology via blogs, wikis, social networking tools, and multiplayer games to connect, communicate, network, and entertain; many of these individuals appreciate the thrill of immediate self-publishing and feel inspired by their online dynamic interactions. Additionally, the transition from Web 1.0 to 2.0 has been impressive over the past decade. People do not only read and retrieve data, but also generate and exchange data (Huang, 2019).

Web 2.0 applications, indeed, exploit the Web's participatory ability. Consequently, Web 2.0 connectivity has become an important component of the everyday and academic lives of many students (Sumner, 2018). Tens of thousands of educators have begun experimenting with the resources given by Web 2.0, and this pattern is no exception in the field of second language (L2) education. Therefore, it can be concluded that the future effect of Web 2.0 technology on language learning and teaching is groundbreaking (Wang and Vásquez, 2012) & AŞIKSOY (2018).

For instance, a blog offers an excellent opportunity to answer the questions of students at any suitable time to address the problems of the proposed subject. One of the benefits of a teaching blog is the upload of a package of documents essential for the learner in the learning process (the curriculum for the discipline, the proposed individual teacher program, rating plan, schedule of teacher consultations, etc.).

Using a blog encourages the autonomous behavior of students, increases enthusiasm, autonomy, and contributes to increased self-control in the learning process, the ability to know and find the data you need. Therefore, the student's interest determines the amount of time spent on planning assignments, designing projects, etc.

The standard of work is also increased as the reach of the lesson does not restrict the pupil. The student will post his/her content, presentations and leave his/her judgments while using the forum, which will be open to the whole group of students.

This study explores the current state of research on Web 2.0 technology (blogs and vlogs, videoconferencing) and L2 learning, investigate the theoretical perspectives framing the recent research, and identify some of the benefits of using blogging technologies in L2 education, and pinpoint possible limitations in the existing research. This study is also designed to propose possible directions for future research.

1. Literature Review

In terms of language concerns, researchers have also examined community, literacy, peer input, engagement, dialogue, knowledge building, communication skills, and comparisons of instructional methods, apart from concentrating on the traditional four language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing).

Researchers have studied learners' attitudes and expectations, personalities, motivation, autonomy, and learning cultures. Researchers have compared the impact of various technical tools on L2 learning within the third technology group.

In short, the language learning environments created by Web 2.0 innovations tend to have extended the reach of technology and language learning study, which has traditionally been more confined to concentrating on the four conventional language skills. Web

2.0 learning environments have provided new contexts for exploring new literacies, new genres, new identities and new pedagogies Cong-Lem (2018).

In this regard, various studies have investigated this integration. For instance, the study Lee (2017) discusses how the L2 writing process was facilitated by the application of blog assignments and how blogging influences the way students interpret blog-based L2 writing guidance and peer input. Akdağ and Özkan (2017) aim to determine whether writing blogs affect the writing abilities of high school students or not. The results suggest that a blog is a valuable method for learners to develop their ability to write in English. Besides, blogging has increased the eagerness of students to write and facilitate autonomous learning. They also suggest that writing blogs are of outstanding value and have the potential for more research for English learners, language teachers, content creators, and curriculum designers.

Alsamadani (2018) conducted a study that lasted for 14 weeks to optimize the blogging for students' individual and group writing skills. The study results disclose that blogging has revolutionized EFL pedagogy and methodology, unlike traditional ways of improving writing skills (learning and teaching). Blogging-based writing practice is more participatory and interactive in that learners can dramatically improve their writing skills in terms of content, word choice, style, language mechanics, and the like. This study recommends that blogging be part of writing classes and be incorporated into school curricula.

In terms of video-blogging, Rakhmanina and Kusumaningrum (2017) conducted a study to find out the difference between video-blogging strategy and expository strategy for teaching speaking. It was found out that learning speaking through video-blogging is more effective than expository strategy. In conclusion, it is recommended that teachers apply the video-blogging techniques in teaching students speaking to promote students' learning motivation. It is essential to give students a chance to develop their own ideas and share their video-blog (vlog).

Degeng and Degeng (2018) emphasize that a significant component of learning any language is self-confidence. Therefore, teachers' task is to coordinate joyful learning using different ways to build the self-confidence of students. They propose that teachers use video blogging as one of the results of technology growth to build the self-confidence of students in language learning.

Lin (2019) in a blog-supported composition class in Taiwan, another research was carried out on a group of first-year EFL college students. The participants held journal blogs inside a language blogging group (LBC) to develop their writing skills, where users could obtain free support (e.g.,

corrections/comments) from native speakers about entries written in a second/foreign language (in this case, English).

Before and after the lectures, students' writing skills and learning attitudes (anxiety about writing) were evaluated (through multifaceted examination). The findings show that the participants developed active blogging patterns over the sessions and articulated them better on their own, using more linguistic knowledge. These promising signs mirrored the enhanced compositional abilities of the students and decreased anxiety. Additionally, the study presented by Giannikas (2019) the effects of integration of blogs as virtual learning with teenage language patterns. The results showed that blogging could help today's language learner improve their literacy and collaborative skills in a motivated and efficient manner.

Gareyev, Shikhova, Shikhov, and Krasavina (2018) mentions that blogging allows students to choose the blog's topic (from the given list or one's own), which motivates a student to do exercises regularly and at a high quality.

Garcia, Moizer, Wilkins, and Haddoud (2019) explore whether higher education students perceive that they learn through blogging, and 600 HE students in the UK and US participated in the study. It was found that students do feel that they achieve higher degrees of learning through blogging. Also, student views were influenced by attitudes to technology, blogging expectations, and previous blogging experiences.

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) through blogging affects the writing ability of EFL students across self-efficacy levels was introduced by Sadiyah and Cahyono (2019) and the finding disclosed that the students utilizing *PjBL* through blogging got better scores in writing than the ones using the traditional method.

Also, Zahrah (n.d.) aims to provide understanding about integrating blogs in EFL class. The findings from the data analysis outline that the students perceive blogs as a beneficial application for English language learning in the areas of writing and reading.

In this line of research in a study Aydin and Özdemir (2020) conducted with 48 students, concluded that the English writing experience using a blog is more motivating than writing using a pencil and paper. It has been observed that there was an improvement in writing, and students liked writing down their ideas and got pleasure from a creative writing assignment. Authors point out that EFL teachers need to know that blogs do not increase motivation among Turkish EFL learners. To increase their motivation level, it is also recommended that teachers should use a writing environment where their students are encouraged to write in the target language.

Jarrah, Falah Alzubi, et al. (2021) concluded that they got positive results after using blogs, vlogs as a language learning tool.

Indrastana and Rinda (2021) using qualitative research approach and holding meetings (1 meeting per week, including lecturing classes and practicum classes preparation, modeling, concept making implementation, and review. The YouTube vlog implementation may benefit students' engagement and confidence to speak English, facilitate students' creativity, and increase students' critical thinking.

In a study Collier and Gallagher (2020), authors viewed the collaborative professional learning opportunity among school district teachers and pre-service teachers as an ideal research project to garner further understandings of how to connect theory and practice for both teachers and pre-service teachers while using blogging as writing and assessment tool with elementary students.

The findings: These findings are clustered in themes related to lines of communication and levels of collaboration; pedagogical approaches to blogging and writing; effective ways of enacting formative assessment in the blogging platform; student learning writing success through blogging, connecting pre-service teachers' academic and personal experiences with the practice.

The results showed that the student felt a sense of validation. Also, students were able to build relationships, increased awareness. Moreover, teachers could connect theory and practice as writing teachers also students were more focused on the holistic message in writing rather than grammar. Perry (2021) education helped students get self-reflection self-identified weaknesses, reducing anxiety and enhancing accuracy. It forced them to reflect on their oral language skills more confidently. It increased their participation compared to speaking in class—high levels of satisfaction and motivation with authentic communication tools.

2. Raised awareness and possible re-positioning

Language learning can be more entertaining, inspiring, and collaborative with Web 2.0 tools and their interactive, social, and collaborative functionality. The following state-of-the-art and their results indicate that the integration of blogging and vlog resources has great potential to benefit language learning and teaching by multiple means.

Students may develop vital skills and language learning skills such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving, analytical skills, especially in the 21st century, through activities designed with these Web 2.0 resources. In the meantime, the drawbacks of using Web 2.0 resources and their intrinsic limitations coexist with advantages and various authors of current literatures suggested.

3. Possible interventions

There is clear evidence of positive results for both learning and inclusion associated with the use of Learning 2.0, demonstrated by enhanced accessibility and accessibility of hard-to-reach learning opportunities, increased motivation and interest in learning participation, overall development of the skills and competencies of learners, and positive impacts on social integration.

In terms of Web 2.0 use, we aim to advocate for a new perspective to encourage future research on studying the interaction and interrelation of blogging and vlogs. The possible intervention regarding methodological issues, the similar types of methodological concerns identified in study persist in the contemporary reviewed studies, such as the lack of depth in research analysis and methodological robustness of research designs.

The research is still at its early stage on the potential contributions of blog to language learning. More research can help decide if the blogging process is significantly affected by other variables such as gender, age, the field of study, computer literacy, and learner personality.

Therefore, we advocate that more work is required to improve accreditation procedures and standards and Learning 2.0 protocols. That can help bridge the gaps between it and the traditional establishment of education.

To promote the progress of Learning 2.0 initiatives i.e. blogs, video-conferences, and video-blogging, the right alliances, combined with the required levels of sustainable funding, are essential. Further research is necessary to gather evidence of Learning 2.0's cost-effectiveness to feed into future business models and policy interventions to encourage further growth.

Additionally, in the writing of their own academic blogs, blogging also requires students to have clear guidance and approval. Furthermore, there is, however, a common awareness among students that the goals and learning results are valuable in writing their own academic blogs for their current and future multimodal learning requires guidance and confirmation.

4. Conclusion

When used constructively and creatively as part of the learning process, blogging has a positive effect on student learning, develops writing process skills, and contributes to a community of writers in the classroom, working with its affordances to respond to the needs of class and individual students. For the students, the blogging format was important and inspiring and also inherently conducive to providing visible input to teachers. It is well known that blogs encourage communication and have the opportunity to track individual students' learning development.

Nevertheless, we are left with the belief that blogging can promote curricular integration as a tool, is open to teachers, can be applied in a number of ways, and offers rewards for student involvement and writing. For the most part, blogging seems to be both an encouraging activity and one that can boost the ability of both teachers to provide formative input and the writing skills of students.

Despite the advantages of an asynchronous communication, while they had a personal (face-to-face) connection with the students, the pre-service instructor experience was the most positive - this could also be done by videoconferencing.

We therefore advocate that further work is needed to strengthen the processes and requirements of accreditation and Learning 2.0 protocols. That can help to bridge the gaps between it and the conventional education establishment.

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